

THE PECULIARITY OF THE SPEECH OF A LAWYER

Isayeva Ozoda Boboqulovna¹

¹ Academic Lyceum of Termez branch of TSTU named after I. Karimov

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5062280>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 20th June 2021

Accepted: 25th June 2021

Online: 30th June 2021

KEY WORDS

internal speech, external speech, oral and written form of speech, components of speech, elite (full-featured), middle literary, literary and non-verbal forms of speech culture

ABSTRACT

There are many professions in the world that are more difficult and honorable than each other. There are many professions, but there are professionals who are distinguished by the uniqueness and richness of their profession. This is the profession of law. As we study their performance, we encounter the diversity of language styles and the diversity of terms used. A noteworthy aspect is that these professionals use certain terms in investigations, inquiries, and other processes. For example, the use of the name of the scene, person named A or person named B is a peculiarity of the change of names. These professionals do not disclose the crime and place and the identity of the person who committed it. uses terms that are difficult to understand. This is also reflected in court proceedings. The terms used in lawyers' speeches, such as investigator, inquirer, victim, scene, murder, murderer, witness, etc., also have a special meaning.

Speech culture is part of human general culture the idea is correct, free, in accordance with the norms of literary language, is a clear, logically consistent, pleasing, and impressive statement. Especially with lawyers in public life communicate, different categories of people {witnesses, victims, culprits, criminals, etc. b.) they come. Extreme caution in their investigation and trial is evident in his attitude to language. In addition, imagining the activities of lawyers without official documents will not happen. Various protocols related to the investigation bibn filling, court verdict, preparation of indictment, and more They are also very literate in writing official documents depends on the ability to use

language tools. So, the future lawyer himself is a skilled speaker, and his speech is logical and The demand of the period to be effective. But for now pre-official documents to jurisprudence networks state tih based on the norms of literary language, in accordance with the rules without which the training will not be at the required level.

The speech culture of our future lawyers to improve, awalo, free on political issues writing essays {For example, "Independence means law", "What is a threat to security?", "Terrorism is a disaster", "Man rights - the highest value ", etc.), the content of small texts Exercises such as extension, text correction

expedient. Such exercises are, first of all, the student secondly, it helps to develop the ability to think his ability to compose logically consistent sentences, texts improves word choice skills.

Any idea, concept, sign, action or attitude to the law is expressed in words, ie consists of words, phrases, terms and terms attitude until it falls into the pattern of expression, the form of expression, social communication, treatment (thinking) does not occur. The reality of the idea, especially the legal idea, is also present also appears in the language. Without language, without words, nothing is clear and there will be no ready-made legal opinion. Thought in legal language words, terms, and a particular structure formed with their participation syntactic devices are formed only through speech models and finds expression in speech: language is a 'living' condition of law. That is why language and law serve society social, spiritual-enlightenment and mental phenomena, language inspires law.

Legal language, by its very nature, is of several types, viz language of law, language of scientific jurisprudence, language of court, language of legal pedagogue, language of lawyer-publicist, language of prosecutor, language of lawyer are divided into groups such as language ^ .Related to the branches of jurisprudence to each other with the commonality of lexical-grammatical features although close, but also has its own characteristics. For example, in the activities of the civil court (party, dispute, litigation, decision, securing a claim) terms in the activities of a criminal court Terms used (fraud, genocide, rape, radically different from terrorism.

It is well known that the law is a means of regulating society, it serves human interests and needs. Of the law content, essence, quality, prestige depends on the rules of language also depends on compliance. The rule of law, too it is determined by its structure on the basis of literary language norms. A law that does not fully meet the norms of literary language the content and logic are incomprehensible. Till the law is the official legal language of the state and citizens with the state is a means of "communication," "communication," between.

For example, alibi - at the time of the crime (instantaneously) the offender's presence elsewhere; ratification - international signing the contract; simulation - from lying to disease hit; jurisdiction - the right to sue, etc. In the legal language, dialect prefixes, jargons, are not mastered it is not allowed to use words, very figurative expressions.

The language of the law is the core of the legal system.

The main features of the language of the law are:

- a) accuracy; b) brevity; c) impersonality; d) official painting;
- e) impartiality; f) logical consistency; j) stability.

Another distinctive feature of the language of law impersonality. That is, the cut of the articles of the law is invalid represented by the relative fe'Uar. In the passive participle of the verb although the object is known, the subject is unknown. For example, cases are heard openly in all courts. The function is closed to be considered in the majhs only in the

hoUarda prescribed by law (Courts of the Republic of Uzbekistan Law on ", p. 55).

Every procedural document is not only legal be linguistically flawless and well-structured should. To the extent that it conforms to the norms of law and language culture The texts are fair to both law enforcement and investigative agencies

also enhances the status of the judiciary, the legal case makes the decision clear.

In this case the procedural legal documents are verbal a professional who can recover based on cultural skills also directly related to the activities of lawyers.

References:

1. Davlat tili: muammolar va yechimlar. T.: 1999.
2. JalilovX. Notiqlik san'ati. T.: Ó'zbekiston, 1976.
3. Jumaniyozov R., Salimov D. G'oyaviy tarbiyada notiqlik san'ati. T.: 2002.
4. aropcKHii F.H. Cyji;e6Haa pent. M.: POpHflH^ecKaH JiHxepaxypa, 1985.
5. Ibrohimov D. Nutq madaniyati va adabiy talaffuz haqida. T.: Fan, 1972.
6. HsaKHHa H.H. ÓCHOBBI cyaeSHoro KpacHopeqiw (puropHKa mn lopHCTOB). YqeHoe noco6He. M.: lOpHcx, 2000.
7. Ko'chimov SH.N. Ó'zbekiston Respublikasida qonunchilik texnikasi (til, uslub, huquqiy atamashunoslik). T.: 1996.
8. JIHKac A.JI. Kyjibxypa npaBocy;i;Ha. M.: lOpHaH^ecKaii .nirrepaTypa, 1990.